

Table 1. Sanders Twitter Corpus (STC) Dataset

Sr No.	Category	Sample Query "String"	Positive Tweets	Negative Tweets	Considered Tweets
1	Apple	apple	164	316	480
2	Google	google	202	57	259
3	Microsoft	microsoft	91	132	223
4	Twitter	twitter	62	67	129
	Total		519	572	1091

Table 2. Twitter Airline Sentiment (TAS) Dataset

Sr No.	Category	Sample Query "String"	Positive Tweets	Negative Tweets	Considered Tweets
1	Virgin America	virgin america	152	181	333
2	United	united	492	2633	3125
3	South West Air	south west air	570	1186	1756
4	Jet Blue	jet blue	544	953	1497
5	US Airways	us airways	74	788	862
	Total		1832	5741	7573

Table 3. Fist GOP Debate (FGD) Dataset

SSr No.	Category	Sample Query "String"	Positive Tweets	Negative Tweets	Considered Tweets
1	Ben Carson	ben carson	164	186	350
2	Chris Christie	chris christie	33	218	251
3	Donald Trump	donald trump	609	1758	2367
4	Jeb Bush	jeb bush	44	589	633
5	John Kasich	john kasich	113	82	195
6	Marco Rubio	marco rubio	119	105	224
7	Mike Huckabee	mike huckabee	73	237	310
8	Ted Cruz	ted cruz	16	11	27
	Total		1171	3186	4357

Table 4. Apple Twitter Corpus (ATC) Dataset

Sr No.	Category	Sample Query "String"	Positive Tweets	Negative Tweets	Considered Tweets
1	Apple	apple	423	1219	1642

Table 5. Stanford Twitter Sentiment (STS) Dataset

Sr No.	Category	Sample Query "String"	Positive Tweets	Negative Tweets	Considered Tweets
1	Company	yahoo, boozallen, at&t, gm, comcast, timewarner, visa, mcdonalds, nike, google, safeway, wieden	33	86	119
2	Person	twitter, goodbye silverstern, aig Cheney, Bobby Flay, Obama, Lebron, Malcolm Gladwell, Pelosi, Fredwilson Danny Gokey, Warren Buffet, Federer	48	17	65
3	Movie	night at the museum, startrek	16	3	19
4	Product	40d, twitter api, 50d, mashable, bing, wolfram alpha, weka, visa card jquery book, espn, kindle2, g2, lakers, iphone app, jquery, wave s&box	47	16	63
5	Location	east palo alto, shoreline amphitheatre san francisco, north korea, iran	3	14	17
6	Misc.	sleep, viral marketing, republican, notre dame school, exam, yankees, lyx, stanford, scrapbooking, surgery,	25	41	66
7	Event	world cup, googleio, indian election	8	0	8
	Total		180	177	357

Table 6. List of parts-of-speech (POS) tags for single word aspects generation using ARM method (used in Penn Treebank Project).

Sr No.	Tags	Description
1	NN	Noun, Singular
2	JJ	Adjective
3	DT	Determiner
4	NNS	Noun - (Plural)
5	NNPS	Proper Noun - (Singular)
6	NNP	Proper Noun - (Plural)
7	RB	Adverb
8	RBS	Adverb - (Superlative)
9	RBR	Adverb - (Comparative)
10	VB	Verb
11	VBG	Verb - (Present Participle)
12	VBN	Verb - (Past Participle)
13	VBD	Verb - (Past Tense)
14	VBZ	Verb - (Singular Present - 3rd Person)
15	VBP	Verb - (Singular Present - non 3rd Person)

Table 7. Multi-word aspects generation using list of POS patterns for tweets dataset.

Sr No.	Tags	Description
1	Nouns	Unigram [NN], bigram [NNS] - [NNP], trigram [NNPS]
2	Nouns - Adverbs	Bigram [NN RB] to Trigram [NN RBS], [NN RBR]
3	Noun - verbs	Bigram [NN VB] to Trigram [NN VBG], [NN VBD], [NN VBZ], [NN VBP]
4	Nouns - adjectives	Bigram [NNJJ], [NNS JJ], [NNP JJ] to Trigram [NNPS JJ]
5	Determiners - Adjectives	Bigram of [DT JJ]

Table 8. Some results of experiments of explicit aspects detection for STS dataset

Sr No.	Category	Single word aspect detection using ARM	Multi-word aspect detection using combination of Heuristic POS Patterns + ARM
1	Product	40, d; twitter, api; 50, d; bing, mashable, weka, visa, card; jquery, book; iphone, app; espn, jundle, 2; g, 2; wave, s, box; wolfram, alpha,	40d, twitter api, 50d, mashable, bing, wolfram alpha, weka, visa card, jquery book, espn, kindle2 features, g2, iphone app, jquery syntax, wave s&box
2	Location	east, palo, alto; san, francisco; north, korea; iran, shoreline, amphitheatre;	east palo alto, shoreline amphitheatre, san francisco, north korea, iran distance
3	Misc.	stanford, notre, dame, school; sleep, republican, surgery, scrapbooking, dentist, lyx, viral, marketing; yankees,	sleep, viral marketing, republican, notre dame school, yankees, lyx, stanford, scrapbooking, surgery room
4	Event	world, cup; india, election; indian, googleio	world cup, googleio, indian election
5	Company	time, warner; safeway, mcdonalds, comcast, wieden, goodby, silverstern; yahoo, google, boozallen, gm, safeway, aig, nike, at, t; visa	yahoo id, boozallen, at&t, gm, comcast, timewarner, visa service, mcdonalds food, google, safeway, wieden, nike quality, twitter account, goodby silverstern, aig
6	Person	cheney, bobby, flay; lebron, barack, obama; fredwilson, malcolm, gladwell; federer, danny, gokey; warren, buffet; pelosi,	Bobby Flay, Obama speech, Lebron player, Malcolm Gladwell, Pelosi, Fredwilson, Danny Gokey, Warren Buffet, Federer
7	Movie	startrek, night, museum;	night at the museum, startrek story

Table 9. Types of dependencies in SDP.

Sr No.	Types	Usage
1	det	Determiner
2	amod	Adjectival
3	aux	Auxiliary
4	doobj	Direct object
5	advmod	Adverbial modifier
6	neg	Negation modifier
7	nsubj	Nominal subject
8	xcomp	Open clausal complement without its own subject.

Table 10. Some extracted implicit aspects from Sanders Twitter Corpus (STC) dataset

Type (Relation)	Dependency Parsing using SDP
xcomp,nsubj,advmod,amod	GOOGLEchrome, MICROSOFTlead, APPLEphone, MICROSOFTcompatibility, GOOGLEconference, TWITTERtweetcharacters, TWITTERmemories

Table 11. Some extracted implicit aspects from Twitter Airline Sentiment (TAS) dataset

Type (Relation)	Dependency Parsing using SDP
xcomp,nsubj,advmod,amod	UNITEDcustomers, USAIRWAYSservice , JETBLUE, VIRGINAMERICAdepart, UNITEDcheapflights, UNITEDskytake, SOUTHAIRWAYSticket

Table 12. Some extracted implicit aspects from First GOP Debate (FGD) dataset

Type (Relation)	Dependency Parsing using SDP
xcomp,nsubj,advmod,amod	CARSONpolitics, CHRISTIEpresident, JOHNspeech, DONALDTRUMPcampaign, MACRORUBIOpoint TRUMPcandidate, GOPDEBATEvote

Table 13. Some implicit extracted aspects from Apple Twitter Corpus (ATC) dataset

Type (Relation)	Dependency Parsing using SDP
xcomp,nsubj,advmod,amod	APPLEprice, APPEmailvoice, AAPLservice, APPLEsaleaccount, APPEreboot, APPLEipad, APPLEitunes, AAPLtweet

Table 14. Some implicit extracted aspects from Stanford Twitter Sentiment (STS) dataset

Type (Relation)	Dependency Parsing using SDP
xcomp,nsubj,advmod,amod	SAFEWAYluke, DENTISTprice, NIKEbasketball, TIMEWARNERinternet, GOOGLEplace, MCDONALDmeal, GLADWELLaudiobook, KINDLE2picture, GOOGLEplaystore, KINDLE2reading, STANFORDschool, LEBRONpuppet, OBAMAspeech, OBAMAspeech, OBAMAslogan, LEBRONcommercial

Table 15. Polarity scores with % of negative, positive and neutral labels in each category of STC dataset

Sr No.	Category	Negative Scores (Polarity)	Positive Scores (Polarity)	Negative%	Positive%	Neutral%
1	Apple	55.24	31.6	27.67%	14.36%	57.97%
2	Google	9.97	38.9	4.33%	15.34%	80.33%
3	Microsoft	23.08	17.5	9.68%	6.67%	83.65%
4	Twitter	11.7	11.95	5.19%	4.90%	90%

Table 16. Polarity scores with % of negative, positive and neutral labels in each category of TAS dataset

Sr No.	Category	Negative Scores (Polarity)	Positive Scores (Polarity)	Negative%	Positive%	Neutral%
1	Virgin America	3.15	8.32	35.91%	30.16%	3.93%
2	United	45.86	26.86	68.89%	12.87%	18.24%
3	South West Air	20.66	31.11	49.01%	23.55%	27.44%
4	Jet Blue	16.61	29.69	42.93%	24.50%	32.57%
5	US Airways	13.73	4.04	77.87%	7.31%	14.82%

Table 17. Polarity scores with % of negative, positive and neutral labels in each category of FGD dataset

Sr No.	Category	Negative Scores (Polarity)	Positive Scores (Polarity)	Negative%	Positive%	Neutral%
1	Ben Carson	5.84	14.01	46.04%	40.59%	13.37%
2	Chris Christie	6.84	2.82	74.40%	11.27%	14.33%
3	Donald Trump	55.18	52.01	62.50%	21.65%	15.85%
4	Jeb Bush	18.49	3.76	83.55%	6.24%	10.21%
5	John Kasich	2.57	9.65	33.88%	46.69%	19.43%
6	Marco Rubio	3.3	10.16	38.18%	43.27%	18.55%
7	Mike Huckabee	7.44	6.23	60.31%	18.58%	21.11%
8	Ted Cruz	0.35	1.37	32.35%	47.06%	20.59%

Table 18. Polarity scores with % of negative, positive and neutral labels in each category of ATC dataset

Sr No.	Category	Negative Scores (Polarity)	Positive Scores (Polarity)	Negative%	Positive%	Neutral%
1	Apple	74.23	25.76	32.05%	11.12%	56.83%

Table 19. Polarity scores with % of negative, positive and neutral labels in each category of STS dataset

Sr No.	Category	Negative Scores (Polarity)	Positive Scores (Polarity)	Negative%	Positive%	Neutral%
1	Company	48.59	18.33	57.20%	23.60%	19.20%
2	Person	9.6	26.67	19.60%	64.80%	15.60%
3	Movie	1.69	8.89	5.30%	78.90%	15.80%
4	Product	9.04	26.11	20.60%	54%	25.40%
5	Location	7.91	1.67	49.00%	21.20%	29.80%
6	Misc.	23.16	13.89	42.60%	31.80%	25.60%
7	Event	0	4.4	0%	82.85%	17.15%

Table 20. Multiple iterations of activation functions of proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) for STC

Iterations	Activation Function	Neurons	Accuracy %	Precision	Recall	F-measure
1	Identity	50,	77.25%	0.775	0.772	0.773
2	Sigmoid	50,	78.99%	0.789	0.789	0.789
3	Tanh	50,	79.25%	0.792	0.792	0.792
4	ReLu	50,	76.88%	0.769	0.768	0.768
5	Identity	50,50	79.85%	0.799	0.798	0.798
6	Sigmoid	50,50	78.88%	0.789	0.788	0.788
7	Tanh	50,50	77.79%	0.778	0.777	0.777
8	ReLu	50,50	76.71%	0.768	0.767	0.767
9	Identity	100,	78.99%	0.789	0.789	0.789
10	Sigmoid	100,	76.25%	0.765	0.762	0.763
11	Tanh	100,	77.25%	0.774	0.772	0.772
12	ReLu	100,	78.99%	0.789	0.789	0.789
13	Identity	100,100	76.25%	0.765	0.762	0.763
14	Sigmoid	100,100	77.25%	0.775	0.772	0.773
15	Tanh	100,100	78.88%	0.788	0.788	0.788
16	ReLu	100,100	79.25%	0.795	0.792	0.793
17	Identity	50,50,50	77.25%	0.775	0.772	0.773
18	Sigmoid	50,50,50	79.25%	0.795	0.792	0.793
19	Tanh	50,50,50	78.99%	0.789	0.789	0.789
20	ReLu	50,50,50	77.25%	0.775	0.772	0.773
21	Identity	100,100,100	78.25%	0.785	0.782	0.783
22	Sigmoid	100,100,100	79.25%	0.795	0.792	0.793
23	Tanh	100,100,100	77.25%	0.775	0.772	0.773
24	ReLu	100,100,100	78.08%	0.788	0.78	0.783

Table 21. Multiple iterations of activation functions of proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) for TAS

Iterations	Activation Function	Neurons	Accuracy %	Precision	Recall	F-measure
1	Identity	50,	82.11%	0.807	0.821	0.813
2	Sigmoid	50,	82.77%	0.819	0.827	0.822
3	Tanh	50,	82.77%	0.818	0.827	0.822
4	ReLu	50,	83.36%	0.825	0.833	0.828
5	Identity	50,50	83.36%	0.822	0.833	0.827
6	Sigmoid	50,50	82.97%	0.824	0.829	0.826
7	Tanh	50,50	84.29%	0.834	0.842	0.837
8	ReLu	50,50	84.22%	0.834	0.842	0.837
9	Identity	100,	82.17%	0.808	0.821	0.814
10	Sigmoid	100,	83.43%	0.827	0.834	0.83
11	Tanh	100,	83.23%	0.828	0.832	0.829
12	ReLu	100,	83.23%	0.824	0.832	0.827
13	Identity	100,100	81.91%	0.806	0.819	0.812
14	Sigmoid	100,100	83.49%	0.829	0.834	0.831
15	Tanh	100,100	83.89%	0.832	0.838	0.834
16	ReLu	100,100	84.15%	0.832	0.841	0.836
17	Identity	50,50,50	83.23%	0.821	0.832	0.826
18	Sigmoid	50,50,50	82.90%	0.823	0.829	0.825
19	Tanh	50,50,50	84.29%	0.835	0.842	0.838
20	ReLu	50,50,50	84.15%	0.832	0.841	0.836
21	Identity	100,100,100	83.03%	0.818	0.83	0.823
22	Sigmoid	100,100,100	82.70%	0.82	0.827	0.823
23	Tanh	100,100,100	84.09%	0.833	0.84	0.836
24	ReLu	100,100,100	83.96%	0.832	0.839	0.835

Table 22. Multiple iterations of activation functions of proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) for FGD

Iterations	Activation Function	Neurons	Accuracy%	Precision	Recall	F-measure
1	Identity	50,	76.72%	0.752	0.767	0.759
2	Sigmoid	50,	77.86%	0.764	0.778	0.77
3	Tanh	50,	77.86%	0.764	0.778	0.77
4	ReLu	50,	78.09%	0.77	0.78	0.774
5	Identity	50,50	80.38%	0.789	0.806	0.797
6	Sigmoid	50,50	80.24%	0.786	0.802	0.793
7	Tanh	50,50	81.15%	0.795	0.811	0.802
8	ReLu	50,50	79.47%	0.784	0.794	0.788
9	Identity	100,	81.54%	0.795	0.811	0.802
10	Sigmoid	100,	76.26%	0.747	0.762	0.754
11	Tanh	100,	78.21%	0.769	0.782	0.775
12	ReLu	100,	79.24%	0.785	0.792	0.788
13	Identity	100,100	80.85%	0.793	0.808	0.8
14	Sigmoid	100,100	80.54%	0.792	0.805	0.798
15	Tanh	100,100	78.55%	0.774	0.785	0.779
16	ReLu	100,100	79.58%	0.789	0.795	0.791
17	Identity	50,50,50	79.12%	0.779	0.791	0.784
18	Sigmoid	50,50,50	75.45%	0.74	0.754	0.746
19	Tanh	50,50,50	79.47%	0.79	0.794	0.791
20	ReLu	50,50,50	80.24%	0.786	0.802	0.793
21	Identity	100,100,100	79.12%	0.779	0.791	0.784
22	Sigmoid	100,100,100	81.15%	0.795	0.811	0.802
23	Tanh	100,100,100	77.86%	0.764	0.778	0.77
24	ReLu	100,100,100	79.12%	0.779	0.791	0.784

Table 23. Multiple iterations of activation functions of proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) for ATC

Iterations	Activation Function	Neurons	Accuracy %	Precision	Recall	F-measure
1	Identity	50,	80.85%	0.793	0.808	0.8
2	Sigmoid	50,	79.93%	0.783	0.799	0.79
3	Tanh	50,	80.85%	0.794	0.808	0.8
4	ReLu	50,	83.23%	0.828	0.832	0.829
5	Identity	50,50	82.77%	0.818	0.827	0.822
6	Sigmoid	50,50	80.54%	0.792	0.805	0.798
7	Tanh	50,50	82.17%	0.808	0.821	0.814
8	ReLu	50,50	82.70%	0.82	0.827	0.823
9	Identity	100,	80.85%	0.793	0.808	0.8
10	Sigmoid	100,	80.54%	0.792	0.805	0.798
11	Tanh	100,	80.24%	0.788	0.802	0.794
12	ReLu	100,	79.93%	0.786	0.799	0.792
13	Identity	100,100	80.85%	0.793	0.808	0.8
14	Sigmoid	100,100	82.17%	0.808	0.821	0.814
15	Tanh	100,100	80.24%	0.79	0.802	0.795
16	ReLu	100,100	82.77%	0.818	0.827	0.822
17	Identity	50,50,50	81.45%	0.799	0.814	0.806
18	Sigmoid	50,50,50	83.05%	0.827	0.813	0.819
19	Tanh	50,50,50	79.63%	0.777	0.796	0.786
20	ReLu	50,50,50	82.58%	0.817	0.824	0.82
21	Identity	100,100,100	81.15%	0.795	0.811	0.802
22	Sigmoid	100,100,100	81.93%	0.802	0.799	0.8
23	Tanh	100,100,100	79.93%	0.783	0.799	0.79
24	ReLu	100,100,100	82.77%	0.818	0.827	0.822

Table 24. Multiple iterations of activation functions of proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) for STS

Iterations	Activation Function	Neurons	Accuracy %	Precision	Recall	F-measure
1	Identity	50,	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
2	Sigmoid	50,	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
3	Tanh	50,	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
4	ReLu	50,	86.19%	0.875	0.861	0.867
5	Identity	50,50	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
6	Sigmoid	50,50	83.33%	0.856	0.833	0.844
7	Tanh	50,50	83.33%	0.84	0.833	0.836
8	ReLu	50,50	84.72%	0.857	0.847	0.851
9	Identity	100,	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
10	Sigmoid	100,	80.55%	0.838	0.805	0.821
11	Tanh	100,	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
12	ReLu	100,	86.11%	0.875	0.861	0.867
13	Identity	100,100	80.55%	0.838	0.805	0.821
14	Sigmoid	100,100	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
15	Tanh	100,100	84.72%	0.857	0.847	0.851
16	ReLu	100,100	83.33%	0.84	0.833	0.836
17	Identity	50,50,50	81.94%	0.847	0.819	0.832
18	Sigmoid	50,50,50	86.11%	0.875	0.861	0.867
19	Tanh	50,50,50	86.11%	0.875	0.861	0.867
20	ReLu	50,50,50	86.11%	0.884	0.861	0.872
21	Identity	100,100,100	80.55%	0.838	0.805	0.821
22	Sigmoid	100,100,100	84.72%	0.857	0.847	0.851
23	Tanh	100,100,100	84.72%	0.851	0.847	0.848
24	ReLu	100,100,100	84.72%	0.875	0.847	0.86

Table 25. General comparison of MuLeHyABSC - proposed system's achieved results with existing benchmark 1

Approach	Features	Accuracy %	Precision	Recall	F-measure	Execution time
MuLeHyABSC+MLP (STC dataset)-Proposed System	POS tags+unigram	78.99%	0.79	0.789	0.789	0.17 sec
Existing Method - Zainuddin et al. (STC dataset)	POS tags+unigram	74.24%	0.751	0.742	0.738	N/A
MuLeHyABSC+MLP (STS dataset)-Proposed System	POS tags+unigram	84.72%	0.851	0.847	0.848	0.14 sec
Existing Method - Zainuddin et al. (STS dataset)	POS tags	76.55%	0.779	0.766	0.76	N/A

Table 26. General comparison of MuLeHyABSC - proposed System's achieved results with existing benchmark 2

Approach	Features	Accuracy %
MuLeHyABSC+MLP (STS dataset) - Proposed System	POS tags+unigram	84.72%
Naïve Bayes - Existing Method Alec Go et al.	unigram+bigram	82.70%
MaxEnt - Existing Method Alec Go et al.	unigram+bigram	83%
SVM - Existing Method Alec Go et al.	unigram	82.20%

Figure 1. Comparison method for proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) using different approaches for STC

Figure 2. Comparison method for proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) using different approaches for TAS

Figure 3. Comparison method for proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) using different approaches for FGD

Figure 4. Comparison method for proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) using different approaches for ATC

Figure 5. Comparison method for proposed approach (MuLeHyABSC) using different approaches for STS

Figure 6. General evaluation of proposed model (MuLeHyABSC) vs existing benchmark 1

Figure 7. General evaluation of proposed model (MuLeHyABSC) vs existing benchmark 2